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Exploring the Role of Parental Involvement in Shaping Learner's Academic Achievement

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic caused significant disruptions in global educational systems, with long-term impacts on early childhood education. This study examines the role of parental involvement in the academic achievement of Grade One pupils, particularly in the context of remote and hybrid learning models. As schools like San Rafael Elementary School adapted to the challenges of the pandemic, teachers and administrators worked tirelessly to implement learning recovery plans aligned with the Department of Education and the Schools Division Office of Rizal's initiatives. These efforts aimed to meet the heightened demand for educational support during this unprecedented time. Data was collected through surveys of parents and educators, as well as academic achievement records from the 2022–2023 school year. The results revealed that high parental involvement significantly contributed to improved academic achievement among students, underscoring the vital role of parents in mitigating the challenges posed by remote learning. In contrast, students with limited parental support experienced deeper learning gaps that persisted beyond the pandemic's immediate effects. The study concludes by proposing an intervention program to address these disparities, focusing on equipping parents with the necessary resources and skills to effectively support their children's education.

Keywords: *parental involvement, academic achievement, parents, intervention*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the world in profound and unimaginable ways. As we reflect on the past two years, its harsh effects continue reverberating, with one of the most impacted sectors being education. Neither global systems nor educational institutions were prepared to transition from traditional face-to-face learning to alternative modalities. In this new normal, the home has become the classroom, and the learning spaces have shifted to delivery modalities that prioritize safety while ensuring educational continuity. Despite the ongoing challenges of the pandemic, education has found ways to adapt and thrive.

As of August 2020, UNESCO recorded that 673,114,704 students—38.4% of the global student population—were affected by school closures, with 30 countries fully closing their schools. These national closures impacted more than 60% of the world's students. While some countries implemented localized closures, affecting millions more, governments across the globe temporarily shut down educational institutions to control the spread of the virus.

In response to these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines prioritized the health, safety, and well-being of learners, parents, and teachers in its decision-making process for continuing education. The department selected different learning modalities to suit these priorities while also considering the diverse needs of students and teachers. After two years of school closures, the Philippines began the gradual resumption of face-to-face classes, with students eager to return, believing that in-person learning with teacher guidance was more effective.

Even before the pandemic, concerns over the quality of basic education in the Philippines were raised, as the country ranked lowest in regional and international learning assessments. The pandemic exacerbated these challenges, and DepEd has sought innovative strategies to address these long-standing issues while working to achieve positive learning outcomes as students transition back to face-to-face instruction. Bridging these gaps has required collaborating with teachers, parents, and other stakeholders.

Children's education flourishes when the significant adults—parents, teachers, and other family members—work together to support and encourage them. Schools alone cannot meet all of a child's developmental and educational needs; parental involvement and community support are crucial. Strong partnerships between schools and families are fundamental to children's success. However, these relationships must extend beyond the classroom as children continue to learn about values, relationships, and academics at home. The involvement of both teachers and parents shapes children's self-confidence, their understanding of the world, and their belief in where they belong in society.

Parental involvement is a critical factor in student achievement, particularly in traditional school settings. The pandemic, however, presented new challenges for parents, who had to take on unfamiliar roles as both caregivers and educators, especially in modular learning. According to Hoover-Dempsey et al. (2005), several factors influence a parent's ability to contribute to their child's education: beliefs about their role, invitations from teachers, socioeconomic status, and their confidence in supporting learning.

The COVID-19 pandemic placed immense pressure on parents to shoulder educating their children. As home-based learning became the norm, parents were expected to act as supervisors, tutors, and home teachers. This sudden shift presented various challenges—instructional, behavioral, financial, and technical—for both students and parents.

Teachers have always played a central role in the learning process, providing emotional and academic support to their students. They create positive, inclusive environments that motivate and inspire learners. Yet, how are parents coping with the demands of this new educational system? This study aims to explore parents' views on educational policies implemented during the pandemic and their experiences with distance learning over the past two school years. It also examines how parents are managing as education transitions to a new normal.

Research indicates that increased parental involvement enhances the effectiveness of children's education (Campbell, 2015). Studies consistently show that parents' contributions lead to better academic and behavioral outcomes for students (Hornby, 2011).

During class discussions and home visits, teachers in our survey found that 87% of parents reported actively helping their children during the pandemic. However, many of those who were not supporting their children said they lacked the necessary teaching skills. This was especially true for parents with lower educational attainment. According to Ilyas (2013), more educated parents tend to have a more encouraging attitude toward their children's studies, providing necessary resources and modern technology for learning.

Filipino families place a high value on educational achievement, viewing it as a means to fulfill familial and social obligations (Sorbring & Lansford, 2019). Despite major education reforms in the Philippines, such as the K-12 law 2013, issues of low quality and inadequate resource allocation persist. Poverty affects student enrollment and completion rates, particularly at the secondary level.

These findings suggest that the pandemic may have exacerbated learning disparities based on parental education levels. Parents have struggled to help their children complete modular learning activities, with common issues including lack of attention, difficulties with the pacing of lessons, incomplete outputs, and even health problems.

Given these challenges, this study seeks to develop an action plan, Project PREACH (Parents' Reactive Empowerment on Aiding their Children at Home), designed to empower parents struggling to facilitate learning. Through collaboration with teachers, parents will gain the knowledge and tools to assist their children effectively, fostering a power-sharing relationship that enhances educational outcomes.

Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic forced schools to adapt in unexpected ways. Teachers felt pressure to maintain pre-pandemic learning standards, while parents were left to take on new roles. By strengthening partnerships between schools and families and providing parents with the tools to support their children's learning, we can ensure that all students receive the education they deserve, even in this new normal. This study explores how parental involvement impacts student achievement and offers strategies to support parents in their critical role as home educators.

Methodology

This qualitative study explored the role of parental involvement on learners' academic achievement, primarily using interviews as the data collection method. An interview is a structured interaction where researchers gather information face-to-face from participants. It is often preferred in qualitative research for its ability to provide deeper insights. The study's main use of interviews was to collect in-depth, extensive information.

Teachers conducted semi-structured interviews with selected parents to explore their experiences, beliefs, and practices regarding their child's education. In addition to interviews, survey questionnaires were employed to collect data on parental involvement, including communication with teachers, participation in school activities, and support for learning at home. Academic achievement data, such as grades, were also analyzed to understand how parental involvement influences student performance.

The qualitative data provided rich insights into parental contributions, such as helping with schoolwork, establishing study routines, and creating supportive learning environments. The study used purposive sampling, a non-probability method where researchers select participants based on specific characteristics relevant to the research questions. This approach is particularly useful when the number of potential participants is limited due to the study's objectives and design (Frost, 2020).

Results And Discussion

The results and reflection on the role of parental involvement in academic achievement among Grade One pupils of San Rafael Elementary School reveal important insights into the significance of these two factors.

The perceptions of Grade One teachers regarding the role of parental involvement in the learner's academic achievement can vary based on their experiences, observations, and interactions with both students and parents. Many teachers believe active parental involvement positively contributes to the learner's academic achievement. They perceive that pupils whose parents are engaged in their education tend to perform better in class, complete assignments, and show enthusiasm for learning. Parents engage in their child's education, and teachers might notice increased confidence and motivation among pupils. They feel more empowered to participate in class, ask questions, and take academic risks. It's important to note that teachers' perceptions can be influenced by their unique experiences, the specific school context, and the diversity of the student population. As such, these perceptions provide valuable insights into how teachers recognize and appreciate the role of parental involvement in shaping students' academic achievement during the early stages of their education.

Parents with varying levels of educational attainment contribute to their child's learning experiences at home in diverse ways, and these contributions can impact the child's academic achievement in several ways. The extent and nature of parental involvement can be influenced by factors such as parents' own educational backgrounds, socio-economic status, cultural beliefs, and available resources. Parents with higher educational attainment may be more adept at assisting their children with homework, explaining concepts, and providing assignment guidance. This support can lead to better comprehension, completion, and quality of homework, potentially resulting in improved academic achievement.

Furthermore, Project PREACH improved parental involvement by fostering a strong partnership between parents and educators. These projects aimed to create a collaborative and supportive environment that enhances pupils learning and overall school success. By implementing interventions and strategies, schools can create a welcoming and inclusive environment that encourages parental involvement and strengthens the home-school partnership. Improved parental involvement not only benefits pupils' academic achievements but also contributes to a more supportive and thriving school community.

Conclusion

The findings of this study emphasize the critical role of parental involvement in shaping positive academic outcomes for grade one students. Active parental engagement in education contributes to a supportive learning environment both at home and in school, facilitating improved academic achievement. Programs such as Project PREACH, designed to empower parents and enhance their active role in their children's education, have shown considerable potential in promoting collaboration between parents and educators. This collaboration creates a shared responsibility for student success.

However, the study also highlights that parental involvement is not uniform and may vary according to socioeconomic status, cultural background, and family dynamics. These factors underscore the need for more personalized and culturally sensitive approaches to effectively engage all families in supporting their children's education. Tailoring interventions based on these variables could ensure that parental involvement strategies are inclusive and equitable.

Project PREACH successfully strengthened partnerships between parents and educators by fostering a collaborative and supportive school environment. This initiative highlights that well-implemented interventions can build a more inclusive and welcoming school culture, which not only enhances students' academic outcomes but also cultivates a more engaged and thriving school community. Improved parental involvement thus emerges as a multifaceted benefit, contributing not only to academic achievement but also to the broader social and emotional well-being of students and the school community.

Finally, this study provides valuable insights into the significant role of parental involvement on academic success among grade one students at San Rafael Elementary School. The evidence underscores the effectiveness of initiatives like Project PREACH in fostering meaningful collaboration between home and school, creating a nurturing learning environment, and empowering parents to take an active role in their children's educational experiences. Future research should continue to explore diverse factors influencing parental involvement and its nuanced effects across varied student populations to ensure the development of inclusive and effective educational interventions.

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